

SOME ASPECTS OF ADAPTATION OF EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMS TO PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS

M. Tajiev

Professor, Department of Pedagogical Education and Psychology, Renaissance University,
Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18677663>

Abstract. *This article examines the improvement of the personnel training system through collaboration between the labor market and the education system. Therefore, the priority agenda includes improving the quality and effectiveness of education and training competitive personnel, developing educational materials based on educational technologies and their principles, and implementing them in practice. It is scientifically substantiated that, for the effective organization of the educational process, an updated educational process is the objective basis for its rapid, high-quality adaptation to the credit-modular system, as innovative processes in economic and social life themselves require radical changes in education. It is also demonstrated that sooner or later, teachers cannot remain outside this process, and that traditional teaching methods are an objective factor in the emergence of the necessary need for mastering scientific skills, integrating education and industry, or computerizing learning. To this end, the goal is to improve educational programs based on professional industry standards and organize educational processes on this basis. The article discusses the role and importance of professional standards.*

Keywords: *educational program, teaching materials, design, professional standards, training content, methodology, educational technologies, network qualification frameworks, science, integration of education and production, credit-modular system, modernization of training content, labor protection and standardization, human capital, labor market and labor relations.*

Introduction

It is widely acknowledged that the transition of modernized Uzbekistan to a path of innovative economic development requires improving the National Qualifications System in line with international standards, which will quickly respond to changes in the labor market. This creates the need to adapt educational programs to professional standards in the context of credit modules, which form the foundation for the development of the higher education system. At the same time, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-76 of May 5, 2025, "On additional measures to ensure the quality of education and improve the system of providing educational services" and Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 498 of August 6, 2025, "On the introduction of a system of comprehensive and special state accreditation of organizations providing secondary, vocational, higher, and postgraduate education, as well as personnel retraining and advanced training" [2] developed INDICATORS for the assessment criteria for special state accreditation of educational programs at higher education institutions aimed at improving the quality of the national higher education system and identified urgent issues aimed at improving the quality of education.

The ongoing changes in society pose new challenges for the education system – the question of what to teach and how to teach it is becoming increasingly pressing. The introduction of a credit-modular system will form the basis for a new organization of the higher education system through improved curricula, the creation of integrated professional development courses, and joint educational programs. This will ensure the competitiveness of our education and specialists in the global marketplace.

Problem statement: Improving the system of labor force training based on the labor market and labor relations in Uzbekistan, developing professional qualifications and knowledge, protecting and regulating labor, human capital, continuous learning, and modernizing the content of vocational education, improving the quality and effectiveness of education and training competitive personnel, developing educational technologies and their principles, and developing draft teaching materials and their practical application are considered top priorities today. It is generally accepted that it seems necessary to clarify the essence of education issues as the main factor in the formation of human capital in the upbringing of a new generation capable of satisfying the high demands of the modern labor market, the role of professional standards and modern pedagogical technologies in organizing the joint activities of producers, teachers and students, the international recognition of the national system of assessing qualifications and knowledge, as well as the organization of the educational process in the context of the credit-modular system.

For effectively education, an objective basis has emerged for the rapid, high-quality adaptation of the updated educational process, its labor market, and higher education programs to the credit-modular system, as innovative processes in economic and social life themselves require radical changes in education. Sooner or later, no teacher can remain outside this process. Traditional teaching methods are becoming an objective factor in the emergence of the necessary need to integrate science, education, and industry, or to acquire the qualities of digital technologies in education.

Literary analysis of the problem:

In the context of reforms in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the adaptation of educational programs to professional standards of higher education has been identified as a priority. At the same time, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019, and the Order of the Director of the National Agency for Education Quality Assurance under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the Indicators for the Criteria for Assessing Special State Accreditation of Educational Programs of Higher Education Institutions," INDICATORS for assessing criteria for special state accreditation of educational programs of higher education institutions were developed. These indicators are aimed at increasing the competitiveness of national personnel and the quality of the national higher education system based on international practices, and current issues related to improving education quality were identified.

Solution:

It is broadly recognized that current challenge is to ensure the quality of education in the context of a credit-based education system. To this end, educational programs adapted to international and professional standards are being developed. Article 34 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" stipulates that the State **Educational Standard** for educational

areas, qualification requirements for educational areas, curricula, and programs are developed with the participation of job candidates based on professional standards.

There is a growing consensus that education is the primary factor in the formation of human capital as a solution to these priority tasks, human capital and professional standards are becoming key concepts of the modern era. The question arises: why update higher education programs, especially subject programs (curricula), which form the foundation of the educational process? It is noteworthy that some subjects in the curricula of educational areas (specialties) at higher education institutions are not in demand in the workplace, which raises objections from employers and young graduates. Because, as our head of state has said, our youth are not the youth of yesterday, but a renewed Uzbekistan, opening up to the world. As in all areas, issues of internationalization and integration have become paramount in education. Higher education institutions where students study, the subjects taught, and the programs used must meet international standards, labor market requirements, and the needs of employers.

Starting in the 2021/2022 academic year, all public and private higher education institutions have transitioned to a credit-modular education system. Educational processes are organized based on learning outcomes, and the learning process itself, curriculum, and programs are designed to ensure the achievement of these outcomes. Therefore, it is crucial to identify, ensure effectiveness, and continually update the universal and professional competencies required by society and the labor market for graduates.

For addressing these issues, based on the National Qualifications Framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 287 of May 15, 2020, "On Measures to Organize the Activities of the National System for the Development of Professional Qualifications, Knowledge, and Skills in the Republic of Uzbekistan," state and economic authorities, together with employer associations, have developed qualification frameworks for industries reflecting the specifics of the corresponding qualification levels. The National Qualifications Framework is intended to address important issues in the implementation of such tasks as the preparation of sectoral qualification frameworks, the development of professional standards, and the updating of vocational and higher education standards based on them.

Professional standards are designed to define the job responsibilities of employees, plan their professional development, train specialists, select employees, develop requirements for employment and work activities, organize training, and justify decisions made during the certification of managers and specialists. It is commonly observed that professional standards are an important document (literally a bridge) between the labor market and the education sector. Their purpose is to ensure that state educational standards, qualification requirements, and training programs meet the demands and needs of the labor market, as well as to guarantee the quality of professional training for qualified personnel. The development of professional standards is a multi-stage and labor-intensive process. The next task was to update state educational standards, qualification requirements for educational fields and specialties, curricula, and natural science programs by adapting them to professional standards. Thus, "the role of educational and regulatory documents adapted to professional standards and international standards in ensuring the quality of education is incomparable." When developing professional standards, the following important criteria are taken into account:

national socioeconomic development trends in the medium and long term;
labor market requirements;

advanced technologies, raw materials, and modern equipment used in production and service delivery.

Employers use professional standards in the following cases:

defining employee responsibilities for drafting employment contracts and job descriptions;

describing job requirements and ensuring their quality;

eliminating duplication of responsibilities;

classifying professional activities and assigning qualification categories to employees;

developing a remuneration system taking into account the specifics of production, labor, and management;

developing an incentive system and determining the types and amounts of incentive payments;

maintaining HR policies.

Developing professional standards is a multi-stage and labor-intensive process that requires not only an initiator but also a responsible person. Organizing an effective working group of developers is crucial. This group should include an organization willing to assume responsibility for coordinating the development of professional standards and ensuring compliance with key requirements.

The next task is updating educational programs in accordance with professional standards. Analysis also reveals significant challenges in this regard. We know that the primary objective of the continuous education system and the activities of teachers is the place, the lesson—that is, the lesson itself. Currently, all educational institutions at best utilize methods inherited from their ancestors, but in reality, they exploit the level of professional training and personal development of teachers. There is insufficient evidence to support the claim that we are imparting knowledge to students using modern pedagogical technologies. Today, the level of use of pedagogical technologies by professors and teachers in the educational process is questionable, as our research demonstrates. This unfortunate situation could undermine all efforts undertaken in education. It is no exaggeration to say that education has reached a dead end.

Every teacher must maintain students' attention in the classroom until the end of the lesson and incorporate the knowledge outlined in the subject program (curriculum) and the national virtues that must be instilled in the younger generation into their own lifestyle. At the same time, in imparting this knowledge and virtues to young people, it is necessary to organize educational activities adhering to six principles and more than 30 rules of didactics, utilizing a range of traditional, non-traditional, and more than 200 interactive methods, accessible digital technologies, and teaching materials. Even the most talented teacher cannot cope with this task. To the question "How to do the impossible?" we answer that it is possible. One of the most important aspects of this process is adapting the educational organization to global standards, that is, developing "Professional and Technical Standards" within the "Credit-Modular" education system and adapting the State Educational Standard, qualification requirements, and curriculum (curriculum) to them as the primary means of their practical implementation. Global educators who have conducted research on this problem have found a solution and called it "developing educational materials based on curricula and their principles."

Therefore, it is necessary to utilize the educational technologies they employ. However, for almost 20 years, not a single educator has been able to perfectly apply a number of educational technologies borrowed from abroad. If we determine the cause, we will notice that the pedagogical

technologies imported from abroad are not adapted to our region. However, a group of scientists and young researchers under the leadership of Professor Boriboy Ziyomukhamedov[3] studied foreign educational technologies, determined their original purpose, basic principles and the implementation algorithm and adapted them to our republic, based on the mentality of our teachers.

In practice, it has been successfully tested in a number of higher education institutions in our country. A first-degree diploma was awarded for "Author of the Best Textbook and Study Guide of the Year." However, our national pedagogical technology has not been widely adopted. Upon closer examination, it turns out that educational technology involves the preliminary development of teaching materials, and our teachers are not yet sufficiently skilled in project design. Subsequently, a lesson planning methodology based on the principles of educational technology—that is, a methodological manual—was developed. However, school administrators and teachers are reluctant to implement this pedagogical technology and methodology until they receive the appropriate instructions. Those responsible for its implementation, including academics accustomed to the pedagogy of the former Soviet Union, are reluctant to consider this issue. They are indifferent to this urgently needed work and sometimes even oppose it.

It is an undeniable fact: if higher education institution staff help implement national pedagogical technologies and the methods for their application, the effectiveness of the educational process will increase severalfold. In particular, the role of the Institute for Labor Market Research under the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan in this regard is undoubtedly incomparable. In developed countries, the student mastery rate using pedagogical technologies has reached 95 percent. To achieve this result, national pedagogical technologies and their application methods must be implemented. This requires the will of those working at all stages of the education and training system. For implementing fundamental changes in the system of continuous education and training, it is necessary to develop a lesson plan based on the principles of national pedagogical technologies and the algorithm for their application.

Conclusion:

When conducting a lesson based on these educational technologies, even a low-skilled teacher will be able to deliver it at the required level. If the educational process is built on these considerations, then, undoubtedly, in the near future, the educational process in the higher education system will become the most advanced in the world. For this, we have a historically formed spiritual reserve, scientific potential, as well as a system of educational technologies and national virtues adapted to our region. Let's make this a reality.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019, "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030."
2. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 6, 2025, No. 498, "On the Introduction of a System of Comprehensive and Specialized State Accreditation of Organizations Providing Secondary Specialized, Vocational, Higher, and Postgraduate Education, as well as Retraining and Advanced Training of Personnel."
3. Todjiev M., "Development of Training Activities for Teachers: Modular Technologies in Continuous Education," Monograph, Center for the Development of Higher and Secondary

Specialized Professional Education under the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – T.: "TURON-IKBOL," 2017. – 246 p.